

Glutathione as an Inductor in the Oxidation of Glucose.

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Hopkins (*Biochem. J.*, 1921, 15, 286 ; 1925, 19, 787 ; *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1922, 54, 527 ; 1927, 72, 185) and his pupils notably Harrison (*Biochem. J.*, 1924, 18, 1009), Dixon (*Nature*, 1929, 124, 512), Meldrum (*Biochem. J.*, 1930, 24, 472, 1421) and others were successful in oxidising amino acids, proteins and fats by air in presence of glutathione. They were, however, unable to oxidise carbohydrates in the same manner.

It is of interest to note that roughly two-thirds of the body energy necessary for human life are obtained from the slow combustion of glucose and as the glutathione content of muscles, where animal oxidation is assumed to take place with the highest speed, is small, it can be concluded that glutathione is not the chief catalyst or inductor responsible for carbohydrate oxidation. The glutathione content of different organs is highest in liver (0·21%), in kidney 0·14% and least in muscle (0·05%).

In continuation of our work on induced oxidation of glucose in presence of insulin (Dhar and Dube, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 444), we have carried on experiments on the induced oxidation of glucose in presence of glutathione. We have observed that dilute bromine water can oxidise glutathione solutions without affecting glucose. In all the experiments described in this paper, the glutathione was first oxidised by the addition of dilute bromine water before the glucose was estimated by Fehling's solution. The experimental results show that contrary to the existing opinion, glutathione in solution can induce the oxidation of glucose by air at the ordinary temperature.

EXPERIMENTAL.

All the experiments were carried out at the laboratory temperature of about 25°. In these experiments, a slow current of air was passed through a series of bottles containing 50% caustic potash solution, baryta solution and concentrated sulphuric acid to free the air from

carbon dioxide and bacteria. A measured volume of this carbon dioxide-free air was passed for a definite time through the solution of glucose containing glutathione and other substances such as ferrous hydroxide, cerous hydroxide, cupric hydroxide, manganous hydroxide, sodium phosphate, etc. The glutathione used was obtained from the British Drug Houses, London, and the p_H of 0.05 % solution was 5.5, and did not reduce Fehling's solution. Extra pure glucose from (Merck) was used for the experiments. The volume of the solution to be oxidised was always made up to 100 c. c. by adding distilled water. The p_H of the mixture after oxidation did not materially differ from the p_H before oxidation.

TABLE I.

Glutathione added.	Air passed.	Duration of air passed.	Amount of glucose oxidised in presence of solution of sodium phosphate containing in g.			
			0.00 (=0 c. c.)	0.1440 (=10 c. c.)	0.2880 (=20 c. c.)	0.4320 (=30 c. c.)
0.00 g.	18.0 litres	9 hrs.	0.5 %	3.7 %	4.4 %	6.1 %
0.00	36.5	9	0.8	...	9.2	...
0.00	73.0	30	15.54	...
0.05	18.0	9	2.3	11.2	13.0	15.1
0.05	36.5	9	4.4	...	15.6	...
0.05	73.0	30	50.9	...
0.10	18.0	9	4.0	13.5	...	28.1

TABLE II.

Vol. of air passed = 18 litres during 9 hrs.

Substances used.	Amount added.	Amount of glucose oxidised	
		in absence of glutathione.	in presence of glutathione (=0.05 g.)
Sodium carbonate	0.10 g.	29.7 %	14.0 %
„ bicarbonate	0.10	3.5	8.3
„ sulphite	0.10	15.2	12.2

The results recorded in Tables II and I show that in presence of glutathione, glucose is appreciably oxidised by passing air, and in presence of phosphate the amount of oxidation is increased. It seems that glutathione acts as an inductor in the oxidation of glucose in presence of phosphate. It is well known that the part which

phosphate plays in the animal metabolism is unique. Moreover, when the amount of air or glutathione is increased, the amount of oxidation increases. In presence of sodium carbonate and sodium sulphite, the induced oxidation of glucose in presence of glutathione is retarded.

In catalytic reactions a mixture of two or more catalysts is generally found to be more effective than their additive values. Moreover, in the animal body a group of inductors, *e.g.*, glutathione, internal secretions, vitamins (ascorbic acid) and other reducing substances of blood (*cf. Annual Reports*, 1930, p. 267) seem to take part in inducing the oxidation of food materials. All these inductors are capable of taking up oxygen directly from the air at the ordinary temperature and the oxidation of the inductors possibly leads to the oxidation of the food materials. In order to find out whether the addition of inorganic inductors like ferrous hydroxide, cerous hydroxide to glutathione leads to the greater oxidation of glucose, the following experiments were carried out and results recorded below.

TABLE III.

Oxidation of glucose in presence of inductors, and Ce (OH)₃ and Fe (OH)₂.

Ce(OH)₃ = 0.1069 g. Fe(OH)₂ = 0.0468 g. 10 C.c. glucose solution = 0.2308 g. CuO.

C e r o u s h y d r o x i d e					F e r r o u s h y d r o x i d e		
Air passed (litres).	Duration (hrs.).	Glutathione added.	Na-phosphate added in 20 c. c. of the solution.	Glucose oxidised.	Glutathione added.	Na-phosphate added in 20 c. c. of the solution.	glucose oxidised.
36.5	18	0.00 g.	0.0000 g.	41.7 %	0.00 g.	0.0000 g.	16.4 %
"	"	0.00	0.2880	56.9	0.00	0.2880	18.8
"	"	0.05	0.0000	22.3	0.05	0.0000	13.1
"	"	0.05	0.2880	30.4	0.05	0.2880	16.55
73.0	30	0.00	0.0000	78.76	0.00	0.0000	38.3
"	"	0.00	0.2880	80.3	0.00	0.2880	51.3
"	"	0.05	0.0000	65.9	0.05	0.0000	26.17
"	"	0.05	0.2880	68.5	0.05	0.2880	42.03

TABLE IV a.

Oxidation of glucose in presence of inductors, Ce (OH)₃ and Fe (OH)₂ mixed with varying amounts of Cu (OH)₂.

Ce (OH)₃ = 0.1069 g. Fe (OH)₂ = 0.0468 g. Cu (OH)₂ = 0.0094 to 0.00094 g. 10 C.c. of glucose = 0.2308 g. of CuO. Air passed = 73 litres in 30 hrs.

C e r o u s h y d r o x i d e .				F e r r o u s h y d r o x i d e .	
Cu(OH) ₂ added.	Gluta-thione added.	Na-phosphate added in 20 c. c. of the solution.	Glucose oxidised.	Na-phosphate added in 20 c. c. of the solution	Glucose oxidised.
0.0094 g.	0.00 g.	0.0000 g.	43.07 %	0.0000 g.	39.25 %
0.00094	84.9	..	50.8
0.0094	..	0.2880	71.6	0.2880	57.0
0.00094	86.5	..	61.7
0.0094	0.005	0.0000	27.03	0.0000	34.57
0.00094	35.6	..	44.0
0.0094	..	0.2880	67.8	0.2880	55.0
0.00094	70.5	..	56.1

TABLE IV b.

Oxidation of glucose in presence of inductors, Ce (OH)₃ and Fe (OH)₂ mixed with minute amounts of Mn (OH)₂.

Ce(OH)₃ = 0.1069 g. Fe(OH)₂ = 0.0468 g. Mn(OH)₂ = 0.00328 g. 10 C.c. of glucose soln. = 0.2308 g. of CuO (before oxidation). Air passed = 36.5 litres in 5½ hrs.

Inductors.	Mn (OH) ₂ .	Glucose left after oxidation in terms of CuO.	Glucose oxidised in terms of CuO.	Glucose oxidised.
Cerous hydroxide	0.0000 g.	0.1854 g.	0.0454 g.	19.67 %
.. ..	0.00328	0.1306	0.1002	43.41
Ferrous hydroxide	0.0000	0.2208	0.0100	4.33
.. ..	0.00328	0.1194	0.1114	48.26

The results recorded in Tables III—VI show that the addition of glutathione to cerous or ferrous hydroxide acting as an inductor leads to a decrease in the induced oxidation of glucose. Similarly glutathione also retards the induced oxidation of glucose by mixture of inductors consisting of ferrous hydroxide and cupric hydroxide or cerous and cupric hydroxides. When, however, the amounts of cerous, ferrous, manganous or cupric hydroxide are small and vary from 0.005 to 0.00188 g., the addition of glutathione markedly increases the oxidation of glucose. Similar results have also been obtained in the induced oxidation of tartrates *in vitro*.

Moreover, we have observed that the addition of small amounts of manganese to cerous or ferrous hydroxide acting as inductors in the oxidation of glucose markedly increases the induced oxidation of glucose as will be evident from the results noted in Table IVb.

These observations *in vitro* are in agreement with those recorded *in vivo*. Hart, Steenbock, Waddell and Elvehjem (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1928, 77, 797) showed that the presence of minute amounts of copper is necessary for the utilisation of iron in the formation of hæmoglobin in the red blood corpuscles of the rat. The recent experiments of Orth, Wickwire and Burge (*Science*, 1934, 79, 33) indicate that copper is likewise necessary for the formation of chlorophyll in the leaves of the orange trees. It is interesting to note that cattle grazing on certain types of Florida pasture land develop a nutritional anæmia, just as citrus fruit trees on certain lands become unhealthy and this may be cured by the use of iron and copper.

Similar observations of Lipman and collaborators (*Plant Physiol.*, 1926, 1, 231; 1931, 6, 593) indicate that in the absence of minute quantity of copper the production of flowers is altered. Moreover, with barley in absence of small quantity of copper, not only flower and seed formation but also the growth are adversely affected. Recently Sommer (*ibid.*, p. 339) obtained poor growth with flax, tomatoes and sun flower in the absence of copper but on adding 0.06 part of copper per million parts of the medium, 12 to 40 times as much green matter was produced.

In previous publications (Compare, Dhar, "New Conceptions in Biochemistry," 1932), we have shown that the addition of nitrogenous substances like glycine and alanine or salts of fatty acids like potassium stearate or oleate, retards the induced oxidation of glucose. In the following table, we have recorded the results on the induced oxidation of glucose due to the inductors like ferrous or cerous hy-

hydroxide in presence of glycine or potassium oleate to which glutathione has been added in some cases.

TABLE VII.

Oxidation of glucose mixed with (a) glycine and (b) potassium oleate in presence of inductors, Ce(OH)₃ and Fe(OH)₂.

10 C.c. of glucose = 0.2308 g. of CuO. 36.5 litres of air passed during 13 hrs.

Ce (OH)₃ used = 0.106 g.

	glycine added = 0.1 g.				K-oleate added = 0.1 g.			
	Nil	Nil	0.05	0.05	Nil	Nil	0.05	0.05
Glutathione (g.)...	Nil	Nil	0.05	0.05	Nil	Nil	0.05	0.05
Na-phosphate (g.)...	Nil	0.2880	Nil	0.2880	Nil	0.2880	Nil	0.2880
Glucose oxidised (%) ...	13.3	31.45	8.2	37.6	14.6	19.5	11.4	25.6

Fe(OH)₂ used = 0.0468 g.

	Glycine added = 0.1 g.				K-oleate added = 0.1 g.			
	Nil	Nil	0.05	0.05	Nil	Nil	0.05	0.05
Glutathione (g.)...	Nil	Nil	0.05	0.05	Nil	Nil	0.05	0.05
Na-phosphate (g.)...	Nil	0.2880	Nil	0.2880	Nil	0.2880	Nil	0.2880
Glucose oxidised (%) ...	24.3	49.6	14.4	66.55	41.4	43.5	34.3	45.3

The above table shows that in the absence of phosphate, glutathione appreciably retards the induced oxidation of glucose using ferrous or cerous hydroxide as the main inductor ; but in presence of phosphate, glutathione accelerates this induced oxidation of glucose.

Experiments in Sunlight.

TABLE VIII.

Vol. of air passed = 18 litres during 9 hours. Temp = 47°.

Amount of glucose oxidised in presence of phosphate containing in g.

Glutathione added.	0.0000	0.1440	0.2880	0.4320
	(=0 c. c.)	(=10 c. c.)	(=20 c. c.)	(=30 c. c.)
0.00 g.	2.0%	9.7%	13.0%	18.6%
0.05	3.4	14.3	22.7	28.2
0.10	6.0	17.8	—	—

TABLE IX.

Vol. of air passed = 25 litres during 7 hours. Temp. = 47°.

Photosensitiser.	Amount used.	Amount of glucose oxidised	
		in absence of glutathione.	in presence of glutathione. (= 0.05 g.)
1. Zinc oxide	0.50 g.	17.7%	27.4%
2. Uranium nitrate	0.50 g.	96.2	99.0
3. „ „	0.10 g.	86.1	89.1
4. Ferric nitrate	0.10 g.	77.9	88.3
5. Animal charcoal	0.50 g.	4.5	5.8

TABLE X.

Vol. of air passed = 18 litres during 9 hours. Temp. = 47°.

Substance used.	Amount used.	Amount of glucose oxidised	
		in absence of glutathione.	in presence of glutathione. (= 0.05 g.)
Sodium carbonate ...	0.10 g.	41.3%	29.3%
„ bicarbonate ...	0.10	23.5	32.5

The above results show that in presence of sunlight, the induced oxidation of glucose in presence of glutathione is increased. Photosensitisers markedly accelerate the reaction, whilst animal charcoal is a poor accelerator. It appears, therefore, that sunlight is of importance in enhancing the oxidation of glucose *in vitro* as well as in the animal body.

F. G. Benedict ("The Physiology of Large Reptiles," Carnegie Institution of Washington, 1932, p. 514), has expressed the opinion that the relatively low heat production with cold-blooded animals in comparison with the warm-blooded animals of the same size is due to the difference in the distribution of the blood carrying the three important factors of metabolism, *viz.*, oxygen, nutrients and hormones and that increased blood flow is associated with increased metabolism. In the cold-blooded animals the amount of blood is relatively less than in warm-blooded animal. The heat production in the body

seems to be controlled by the blood supplied to the tissues. Where there is a liberal blood supply to the tissues, the heat generation can be high ; where the blood supply is low the heat production must be low also. The blood distribution is not determined by the metabolism, because with man the same blood distribution may permit his metabolism to be increased 1000% in extreme cases. Lusk (" Science of Nutrition," 1919, p. 105) has stated that in starvation, amongst the various body organs, the greatest loss in weight is suffered by the glands and their activity is greatly reduced. Taking the above points in consideration, it seems likely that the internal secretions acting as inductors largely control animal oxidation. In starvation, the amount of internal secretion available for accelerating the oxidation decreases and hence the metabolism is decreased. In violent exercise, the metabolism is highly increased probably due to the increase in the oxygen intake and a greater supply of internal secretions from the various glands. It appears that although glutathione and other reducing agents present in the blood are of some importance in animal metabolism, the chief inductor seems to be the internal secretions.

SUMMARY.

1. Glucose is appreciably oxidised by air at the ordinary temperature in presence of glutathione. The amount of oxidation increases when phosphates are added.

2. In presence of small amounts of cerous, ferrous, manganous or cupric hydroxide, the addition of glutathione markedly increases the oxidation of glucose. Similarly the addition of small quantities of manganese to cerous or ferrous hydroxide increases the induced oxidation of glucose.

3. The induced oxidation of glucose in presence of glutathione is accelerated by light and photosensitisers further accentuate the reaction.

4. There is no correlation between the glutathione content of animal tissues and the intensity of metabolism. It seems that internal secretions acting as inductors largely control animal oxidation.

